

violations_satellites_split_Jun_2022

doculect	onset_violation	coda_violation	either_violation	both_violation	sib_onset	sib_coda	nas_onset	nas_coda	approx_onset	approx_coda	obs_onset	obs_coda
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mum	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Thalanyji	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-latin	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-gumalu	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mengerrdji	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yingkarta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warnman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-pal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bardi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-kogui	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sumau	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-anamgura	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-faita	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhanda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyikina	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernselekup	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-pulabu	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-cabiyari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-malas	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bau	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-kalaallisut	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Eryuan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Suzhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kungkari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kaantju	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Wenzhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sihan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tariano	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-latvian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-robinsonap-alorpantar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ayapathu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-ket	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Jawoyn	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-musak	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-klon	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyiyaparli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Unggumi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-tamil	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Chengdu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mbabaram	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-southern sami	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Xiangyun	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangarrayi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Limiingan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tucano	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yanyuwa	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yindjibarndi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-korean	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warndarrang	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-lezgian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-portuguese	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northern sami	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-bora	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kartujarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-lemio	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-polish	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-tsez	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
lexibank-zraggenmadang-ukuriguma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuninjku	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-mandarin chinese	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Putjarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-western farsi	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yinhawangka	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-siriano	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-danish	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-northeuralex-bengali	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-chechen	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Patjtjamalh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Murrinh-patha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-turkish	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-bashkir	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-sawila	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Duungidjawan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

lexibank-northeuralex-russian	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
lexibank-robinsonap-wersing	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Angkamuthi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Dyirbal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngaanyatjarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-komipermyak	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-kobol	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-urigina	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkajunga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-giacone	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Shenyang	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarluma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mosimo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-guayabero	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
lexibank-northeuralex-standardarabic	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
lexibank-beidasinitic-Fuzhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-moksha	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Lardil	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-ukrainian	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yaygir	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-maia-pila	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-croatian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Central Arrernte	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Malkana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-ocaina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gidabal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-yuruti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-dimina	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-hillmari	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-kazakh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-estonian	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
lexibank-hubercolumbian-playero	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Muruwari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gamilaraay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kukatja	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-chapalaachi	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nakara	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Walmajarri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Koko Bera	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-blagar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalakgan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Alawa	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-curripaco	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-pamosu	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-silopi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wubuy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-uyajitaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Urningangg	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Payungu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Kunming	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-wamas	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gudanji	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Heqing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-chimila	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-skoltsami	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaalaraay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-evenki	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Emmi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-icelandic	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-standardalbanian	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurr-Goni	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tanimuca	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-dutch	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-kannada	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Xi_an	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-carijona	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenasajja	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-gavak	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-dargwa	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Guwamu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-aleut	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
lexibank-northeuralex-belarusian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyangumarta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-awa	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ritharrngu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Larrakia	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Malngin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

lexibank-northeuralex-french	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-isabi	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mudburra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bularnu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Burarra	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-saep	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Marra	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-panim	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-moderngreek	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-japanese	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-nedebang	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-utarmbung	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-muinane	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-catalan	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Narrungga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-achagua	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bidyara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-kaera	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-nukak	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-korak	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-carapana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotominica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-romanian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-puinave	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuku Yalanji	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-musar	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yorta Yorta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-chuvash	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-wadaginam	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-westernpantar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wulguru	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-kare	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenabasurud	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-siroi	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Chaozhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-armenian	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-kakua	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tsafiqipila	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wayilwan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Biri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-garus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-waskia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-ogea	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Tharrkari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Arrernte	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-kamang	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-manchu	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-moere	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaliyaay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bilakura	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-slovak	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernmansi	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Atampaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-tundranenets	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Worrorra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngandi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-ganglau	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Miriwoong	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Rembarrnga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-forestenets	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-koreguaje	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-centralsiberianyupik	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-malayalam	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Angkula	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Yunlong	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngawun	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-wanano	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangala	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Zhoucheng	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-asas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sileibi	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-kamsa	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-norwegianbokmal	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-macuna	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yadhaykenu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-matepi	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

ausphonlex_v0-4:Wariyangga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Margany	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-migum	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-guahibo	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-ateuble	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-desano	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-yabong	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberatado	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-utu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-lak	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
lexibank-zraggenmadang-miani	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-tatar	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-yoidik	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bakanh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kalkatungu	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Adnyamathanha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyawaygi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gumbaynggir	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Hefei	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-cuiba	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Jianchuan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Djinang	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngardily	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-kui	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wagiman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bagupi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Iwaidja	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-bari	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yarluyandi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gugu Badhun	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ikarranggal	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-jupda	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-inga	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bepour	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Linngithigh	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sop	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Matngele	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-komizyrian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurtjar	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-catio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-kowaki	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Karajarri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yulparija	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-nobonob	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Thaynakwithi	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kunwinjku	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yandruwandha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-ossetian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-abui	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-livonian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-samosa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-danaru	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-nivkh	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberadarien	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mirriny	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-wayuu	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Oikol	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngamini	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Luobenzhuo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-nanai	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-kildinsami	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-northeuralex-telugu	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-lithuanian	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Meixian	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-chukchi	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-avar	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
lexibank-zraggenmadang-apali	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kija	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-resigaro	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Umpila	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-basque	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-olonetskarelian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Eastern Anmatyerre	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nungali	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Amurdak	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Beijing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

lexibank-zraggenmadang-munit	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-kein	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Waanyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-udmurt	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kariyarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Dalabon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlpiri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Pintupi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-waimaja	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Anguthimri	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernuzbek	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-yangulam	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-irish	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-hungarian	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yintyinka	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-adyghe	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
lexibank-northeuralex-northkarelian	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-modernhebrew	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wik Mungkan	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mala	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-italian	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Jiwarli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-czech	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-yucuna	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-buryat	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-rempi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-moresada	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Lanping	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-georgian	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernkhanty	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
lexibank-hubercolumbian-saliba	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-veps	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-northeuralex-breton	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-english	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-lulesami	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-male	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-murupi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-nend	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Badimaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-anam	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-usan	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northazerbaijani	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-hubercolumbian-wounaan	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyamal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-girawa	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarla	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-yarawata	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warluwarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yawijibaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunggari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngadjunmaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Nanchang	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-paynamar	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gun-Djehmi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Southern Paakintyi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Dharumbal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-allenbai-Qiliqiao	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yidiny	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-wagi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-rapting	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-robinsonap-adang	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-brem	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tunebocentral	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-baniva	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-yukpa	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlmanpa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Diyari	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurrama	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangjiang	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhangu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Malyangapa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernpashto	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-southernyukaghir	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-biyom	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-piratapuyo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wotjobaluk	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

ausphonlex_v0-4:Gangulu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wemba Wemba	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kok Nar	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-khalkhamongolian	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-burushaski	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
lexibank-northeuralex-hindi	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernnyukaghir	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-totoro	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-amele	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Watjarri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhirrpi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-barasana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-secoya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-yaben	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhay'yi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-kesawai	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-watiwa	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-erzya	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngijambaa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-nake	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-cubeo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-amaimon	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-jitnu	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tatuyo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Panyjima	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-orejon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Guangzhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangzhou	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-gal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-uya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Jarú	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Tiwi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-paez	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Warrgamay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-spanish	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wanyjirra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Wakaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Mawng	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-german	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Purduna	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-anjam	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Xiamen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-saruga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Erre	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-baimak	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-piapoco	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-siona	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-mirana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Yalarnnga	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Butchulla	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-kalmyk	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Djapu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotomurui	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-waube	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawak	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiradjuri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-hokkaidoainu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sinsauru	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wambaya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Thirarri	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Jinan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wardaman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuugu Ya'u	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Oykangand	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-bara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-tuyuca	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bongu	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-wanambre	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-mauwake	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Unyjan	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-inarisami	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-ika	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-abkhaz	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
lexibank-robinsonap-teiwa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-sakha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bilinarra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

lexibank-zraggenmadang-arawum	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-guambiano	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
ausphonlex_v0-4:Pitta Pitta	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Djabugay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wirangu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-nganasan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-welsh	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
lexibank-zraggenmadang-isebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-beidasinitic-Changsha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-northernkurdish	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Bunuba	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sam	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gooniyandi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Rimanggudinhma	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberachami	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotonipode	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gupapuyngu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-rerau	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Kugu Nganhcara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Waalubal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-jilim	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-slovene	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-sausi	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurindji	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-itelmen	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
lexibank-zraggenmadang-tauya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Guugu Yimidhirr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhangu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-zraggenmadang-bargam	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkumara	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Nukunu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-meadowmari	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Martuthunira	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-finnish	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-swedish	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
lexibank-northeuralex-bulgarian	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0